

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF THE TERMS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In the sphere of lexeme-making, the laws of internal language evolution are self-evident. The evolving models and word-formation procedures linked with its development and improvement are proof of this. One of these processes is known as word creation in modern English. The structural and semantic examination of Uzbek phrases signifying foreign interactions is the focus of this essay.

Introduction

In the field of lexeme-making, the laws of the internal development of language are clear. This is evidenced by the emerging models and methods of word formation associated with its development and improvement. In modern English, one of these methods is called word-formation. Some literature refers to "morphological-syntactic word-formation" and "grammatical-word-formation", while others use the term "lexical-syntactic word-formation". In Uzbek linguistics, the creation of a new term in this way is called "syntactic term creation". Creating a new term by changing the meaning of simple words can increase the richness of vocabulary in many languages in international fields. A large number of international terms have been enriched by changing the meanings of common language words and terms derived from social and economic fields. This method of constructing terms differs from others in that in other cases, if a new form (i.e., a word with a new combination of elements) is recreated to express a new concept, then the new content is replaced by the old form of meaning (i.e., previously existing). The finished word is taken). The peculiarity of creating a term by changing its meaning is that the object is terminated (i.e., the subject or event to be named) always has something in common with the subject or event whose name is used as a term will be. This commonality may be reflected in the similarity between their appearance or the function they perform, and so on. The name of an existing subject can be changed to a new one only if the concepts of these subjects are clear and have a common point of view that connects them, otherwise, it cannot be done. Therefore, when creating terms, it is necessary to pay attention to their meaning and structure. International terms that are structurally and spiritually analyzed are also abbreviated. In our research, we would like to emphasize that in the analysis of them, it is impossible to semantically analyze the abbreviations that exist in the first place. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the words in order to get their full meaning. Semantic syntactic term

formation is more widely used in the social and economic fields than in other fields. The main reason for this can be explained by the fact that the terms of both fields have appeared in the past on the basis of the vernacular and are closely related to the spoken language. Therefore, the transfer of the meaning of many lexemes, which are characteristic of the vernacular, is relatively common in the system of terms in the international arena.

Although affixation of terms in international fields is less effective than syntactic construction, it is important from a diachronic point of view. English is used in many international linguistic settings, especially in word-formation. Therefore, in order to create terms in English (prefixation, suffixation) can use several words or phrases. The following are the principles and methods of making terms in English: With the help of prefixes, terms are formed mainly in English by prefixes (pre, inter, im, re, de, com, con, dis, ex) and a work can indicate whether the action has been performed before or should be performed. This prefix denotes the pre-execution state of an action: Precivilization - before civilization; preannounce - before publication; precalculation - before calculating; pre-Code- before coding; predeposit-before depositing money in the bank; deselection, delicate, desertification, deformation exchange, export, express ensure, entitled discrepancy, discrete, discussion, dispute restructure, revisit, reappear, rebuild, refinance interact, intermix, interface. Morphological factors related to a number of other prefixes are also important in the construction of economic terms in English. Suffixation can be used to create terms in English that act as nouns, pronouns, or verbs. For example, suffixes such as -er, -or, -nt can denote a person performing a certain action, a mechanism: minister, administer, superior, ambassador, physicist, philologist Drier, cutter, computer. The suffixes -ion, -tion, -sion, -ment, -ure, -age can be used to form terms from verbs to nouns. For example collaboration, documentation, resolution, identification mission, expression, admission development, punishment, achievement advantage, baggage, plumage. In addition, new terms are created from adjectives using the suffixes -ism, -ty, -ity, -ness, -ence, -ance. For example fundamentalism, terrorism, extremism, capitalism, separatism, authority, security, quality, responsibility, humanity perseverance, dependence, interference alliance, attendance, acceptance, business. The adjectives and nouns used in the above translation models make it easier to understand the meaning of the word. For example, understanding that the suffixes "less" and "ful" have opposite meanings is not a problem for the translator and allows the translation to be correct: relentless respectful, peaceful, careful. When translating political texts from Uzbek into English, special attention is paid to the construction of certain political terms, and other words of this type can be understood without looking in the dictionary. For example, if we look at the English alternatives to the criteria of priority development in the policy of our state, such words as democratization, modernization, globalization are formed with the addition of the passive form *lashtirish* (in Uzb.). This suffix corresponds to the English suffix -ization, and thus we translators form words by knowing the English meaning of the base of these words (democratization - *demokratlashtirish*, modernization - *modernizatsiya*, globalization - *globallashtirish*). In his works, Professor U. Tursunov provides information on the development of the terminological system of the Uzbek language at the expense of internal and external sources. As in any language, Uzbek uses several methods to express a concept. They include:

1. Semantic enrichment of terms.
2. Morphological construction of terms.
3. Syntactic construction of terms.

Many terminological systems have made effective use of semantic terminology. Because semantic word formation is a constant and traditional way of doing terminology. In the process of examining the terms, it was shown that several lexical layers can be included in the terminological system due to semantic change. They are ordinary words of the Uzbek language that serve to express a meaning.

When a common word is considered a term, one of the concepts or meanings of the word must represent the term and an important feature of the subject. For such words to be terms, they are defined by scholars and their meaning is limited. Then it is noted which field is the term. The semantic development of a word leads to the formation of a new word in the language and serves to enrich the util terminology. In the terminology of the Uzbek language, syntactically formed terms play a more important role than single-word terms. This is due to the fact that syntactically formed terms are an important nominative source in Uzbek, as in all languages. Any change in socio-political life has its mark on its terminology. Socio-political terminology is a normative system such as political system, social and political groups, parties, currents and their representatives, government meetings and institutions, public administration and its bodies, worldviews, property relations, domestic and foreign policy, socio-political documents, ethics divided into groups. Political terminology is mainly newspaper-information style. In the socio-political sphere, the orderliness and seriousness of the terminological system are less observed. Newspapers and information materials often use ambiguous terms, synonyms, abbreviations and names. In political English terminology, the term "legal" is used to mean both "legislative" and "legal". The classification of political terms is as follows:

1. Name of parties: "O'zbekiston Xalq demokratik partiyasi" - The people's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan-Народно Демократическая партия Узбекистана; "Adolat" partiyasi - Justice Social Democratic Party; "Milliy tiklanish" partiyasi - National Revival Democratic Party; Liberal partiya - Liberal Democratic Party -Либеральная партия.
2. Names of alliances, associations and structures: Shanghai hamkorlik tashkiloti-Shanghai Cooperation Organization -Шанхайская организация сотрудничества; Markaziy Osiyo Hamkorligi Tashkiloti-Central Asia Cooperation Organization-Организация Центрально-азиатского сотрудничества; Mustaqil Davlatlar Hamdo'stligi-Commonwealth of Independent States -одружество Независимых Государств; Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti -United Nations -Объединенные Нации; Yevropada Xavfsizlik va Hamkorlik Tashkiloti -Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe Организация побезопасности сотрудничествув Европе; Yevropa Ittifoqi-European Union - Европейский Союз; Xalqaro valyuta fondi- International Monetary Fund-Международный валютный фонд; Jahon banki- The World bank -Всемирный банк; Osiyo taraqqiyot banki -The Asian Development Bank -Азиатский банк развития; Islom taraqqiyot banki -The Islamic Development Bank -Исламский банк развития; Xalqaro uyushma - International association -Международное объединение.

3. Names of political positions: President-the president –президент; tashqi ishlar vaziri - Minister of Foreign Affairs – Министерство Иностранных Дел; diplomat –diplomat – дипломат.

4. Names of political committees: Davlat departamenti - State Department– Государственный департамент; Davlat xavfsizlik qo‘mitasi-Committee for State Security – Комитет государственной безопасности; Xavfsizlik kengashi - Security Council – овет безопасности.

The terminology of official working documents is characterized by its standardization and standardization. Without its knowledge, the translator will not be able to obtain an adequate, official translation of the relevant documents. When it comes to political terminology, the construction of political terms in English is usually done through the spiritual translation of words learned from a foreign language. Therefore, it is often possible for the translator to memorize these words, or at least try to translate them in an attempt to determine the meaning of the word. For example, “Bugun men Qonunchilik palatasi va Senatning birinchi qo‘shma majlisida so‘zga chiqar ekanman, asosiy maqsadim – jamiyatimizni demokratlashtirish va yangilashning konsepsiyasini, shuningdek, mamlakatimizni 2021 yilva kelgusi davrda modernizatsiya va isloh etish bo‘yicha oldimizga qo‘yiladigan asosiy vazifalarni qisqacha bayon etishdir”. “Today I will be narrating at a joint session of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate, the first and the main purpose of the concept of democratization and renewal of society, as well as the country in 2005 and the next period of modernization and reform of the basic outline of the tasks”. The word “Qonunchilik palatasi” in this sentence is derived from the words “legislative” and “chamber” (the Legislative Chamber); The word “Senat” means Senate “muhokamada ishtirok etish”, “maslahatchi, senator”; The word “demokratlashtirish” is derived from the morphemes “democratization”, “people”, “governance” and “demarcation”; As we can see, the peculiarity of the English language is that it is possible to understand the translation of a whole word according to the meaning of individual components of words. Each country has its own electoral system, but there are many commonalities in the technology, goals and objectives of election campaigns. The translation of electoral thematic texts should take into account the specifics of the electoral system of the country of origin and the language of translation: saylov –election, voting; saylovchi –elector, voter, etc. The history of the emergence of socio-political terms in the Uzbek language dates back to antiquity “O‘rxun-enisey”. Terms such as “budun” (meaning “city”), “sab” (meaning “council”), “scribe” (meaning “secretary”), “alp” (meaning “hero”) is a clear example. Changes in socio-political life, of course, are also reflected in its lexical layers. This opinion can be seen in the following socio-political terms in M. Kashgari's “Devonu lug‘otit turk”: buzun, baj, bojun (Meaning “team”), bachig’ (Meaning “covenant”), beg, jarlig’, boj (Meaning “tribe”), jag‘i, bulg‘aq (Meaning “conspiracy”), jer (Meaning “country”) and so on. One of the important features of the socio-political terminology of that time is that some of them are still actively used in Uzbek and Karakalpak and other Turkic languages (el-el, boybay, ont-ant).

The Dictionary of Socio-Political Terms, created by Uzbek linguists, has a special place. The dictionary contains more than 22,000 possible alternatives to Russian-international terms. We believe that such terms as putch, raspiska, sotrudnik, upravlenie, fundament in the Uzbek

language are expressed in the Uzbek language with alternatives such as mamur, dalil, insonparvarlik, qonunshunos, muhojir, fitna, tilxat, poydevor. At the same time, the dictionary has a positive effect on the use of a number of Russian-international terms in the Uzbek language, such as deputat, diplomat, institut, kapitalist, pensiya, respublika, prezidium, syezd, strategiya. Another important feature of the dictionary is that after a certain rucha-baynaminal term, its Uzbek equivalent and compound terms are used to explain the meaning of this term. This can be clearly seen in the translation of qualitative terminology. For example: безрпизорный ребенок-orphan, вредное наследиестарого - harmful remnants of antiquity. The dictionary also tries to use a number of word formation tools of the Uzbek language in the expression of socio-political concepts. In particular, the Persian-Tajik affix -dor, which has become the "property" of the Uzbek language, is effectively used in the dictionary. For example: aksioner shareholder, diktator-the ruler, doverenniyauthorized etc., are among them.

Conclusion

It should be noted that these qualities have contributed to the stabilization of socio-political terms in the Uzbek language. At the same time, in this dictionary, one or another socio-political concept is expressed by different meanings. Given that one of the main principles of this terminology, that is, the emphasis on synonymy is not justified, kvalifikatsiya-qualification // qualification, correspondence -correspondence // article // message // information, opposition - opposition//resistance (now: opposition), polozhenie-law // rule; cannot be said to have been translated correctly in the statute // statute forms. The above conclusions give the following definition of a scientific term: a scientific term is a word that classifies at a certain scientific level in the current system of terminology, turg, with sufficient accuracy to reflect the interaction of the object being terminated with others in its semantic (semantic) structure. is a compound or abbreviation.

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